

Special Relativity, Conservation Laws and Particle-Wave Duality

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One may use the complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed ($-v$) relative to each other to establish a special relativistic relation linking m_0 in a rest frame to E, p in a moving. In particular, this may be done strictly using a matrix (which requires the presence of a constant speed which is the same in all frames), but we note that physically a moving particle has been acted on by a force according to Newton's law. Newton's laws are directly linked to conservation of momentum and energy. Thus, we try to argue that these notions of conservation and interaction should appear in the special relativistic framework, but at first glance it seems that one only obtains equations for particle properties $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ (for a particle with rest mass).

We have suggested in previous notes, however, that the speed c (the same in all frames) which appears in the equations for E and p has physical significance for a particle with rest mass. In particular, we argued that one must consider two solutions: the first $-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0$ to deal with the center-of-mass and the second, $-Et + px = 0$ to deal with the signals (this is also the free photon solution). We argue that the former is linked with particle properties, while the latter, associated with $\Delta t = \hbar/E$, $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is linked with interactions and ultimately conservation of energy and momentum. Thus, both solutions are relevant, but we argue that they are intertwined. One does not have one or the other as is sometimes implied by particle-wave duality.

In other words, the particle-duality which is often associated with a quantum particle appears in special relativity, we argue. We stress that the particle features are key to considering the quantum problem because $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is based on particle properties E and p for a particle with rest mass, even though it is linked with a probabilistic wave-math formalism. We discuss this for both the two-slit and bound state scenarios.

Special Relativity and Conservation Laws

Special relativity seems to be based on the complementarity of two frames moving with a speed $-v$ relative to each other. A particle at rest in one frame is seen to be moving in the other and vice versa suggesting an equation linking m_0 in one frame and E and p in the other.

We have argued in previous notes that one may actually use Newtonian values m_0 , $KE = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ and $p = m_0 v$ to find an approximate relation which may be generalized. Newtonian mechanics deals with forces and accelerations as well with conservation of energy and momentum, ideas which seem absent from the special relativistic complementarity scheme.

One may try to associate: $(m_0 \gamma + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2) (\gamma + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2) - p^2 \approx m_0^2 \gamma^2$ ((1))

Here d is a constant speed which is the same as seen in all frames (which means it does not have a rest mass), but is somehow physically associated with the particle with rest mass m_0 . The idea of an equation is based on the complementarity of frames moving at constant speed relative to each other. More generally, one may use a matrix approach:

$$\left| \frac{g(v)}{v/c} - \frac{g(v)}{g} \right| \quad ((2))$$

Applying ((2)) to (0, modd) one obtains (pd, E) and the complementarity approach suggests that there must be an equation linking the two vectors. If one suggests a modulus type equation, then:

$$Momo \, gg \, dddd - vv \, momo \, dd \, gg = \, momo \, dddd \quad ((3))$$

This suggests $g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/dd}$ ((4)) Note $d=c$, the speed of light in a vacuum.

((4)) is consistent with the approximate Newtonian approach.

The question we ask is: Why should a matrix approach which bypasses Newton's equations and conservation of momentum and energy reproduce Newtonian results?

Conservation of momentum and energy are fundamental ideas linked with the work done to accelerate a rest mass m_0 to constant speed v . These ideas cannot simply disappear in the special relativistic formalism, we argue. These ideas, however, are not properties of a particle, like m_0 , E and p , but are properties of an interaction, i.e.

$$P_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \quad ((5)) \text{ with } p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 \text{ being vectors}$$

How can one introduce the notion of an interaction property into a single particle scheme which is what the Lorentz transformation creates?

We suggest that to do so, one introduces two solutions to the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + px \quad ((4))$$

For a particle with rest mass, $-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0$ (for center-of-mass motion), while for a photon, $-Et + px = 0$. We suggest that a particle with rest mass actually has $-Et + px \neq 0$ for the center-of-mass motion, but $-Et + px = 0$ for a portion linked with the signal c which appears in expressions for E and p . This leads to the notion of:

$$\Delta t = \hbar/E \text{ and } \Delta x = \hbar/p \text{ as well as } \exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((5))$$

We note that unlike m_0 , E and p , Δt and Δx are really interaction properties. At first one might think they are fixed intervals associated with a moving particle, but we suggest that this is not the case.

To see this, first consider a particle moving with momentum p and linked to $\exp(ipx)$. It should produce an interference pattern with a 2-slit system at rest if the slits are about \hbar/p apart. If

the 2-slit apparatus is moving, however, one does not use the p of the particle to define wavelength $= \hbar/p$, but goes into the rest frame of the moving 2-slit system and uses p_1 in that frame to define wavelength $= \hbar/p_1$. In other words, Δx is linked to an overall reaction. As second example is:

$$\exp(i p_1 \cdot r) \exp(i p_2 \cdot r) = \exp(i (p_1+p_2) \cdot r) \quad ((6))$$

Here $|p_1+p_2|$ is used to define an overall wavelength through $\hbar/|p_1+p_2|$ with p_1 and p_2 being vectors.

The wavelength is interaction based and associated with conservation of momentum if one insists on the same wavelength (of the interaction holding for an r vector along p_1+p_2 and p_3+p_4 . Then:

$$P_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4 \quad ((7))$$

In other words, we suggest that the $-Et+px = 0$ c-signal solution for a particle with rest mass is also linked with interaction and conservation of energy and momentum with $\exp(-iEt)$ being linked to energy conservation and $\exp(ipx)$, to momentum conservation.

Particle and Probability Wave Notions

It is sometimes suggested that quantum mechanics deals with particle-wave duality and that one either sees particle features or wave features. For example, a two-slit system is supposed to exhibit wave behaviour, but we argue that particle features are still strongly present. We first note that special relativity for a particle with rest mass is strongly based on a particle picture because a particle at rest is seen to move with momentum $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and:

$$E = mocc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ approx} = mocc + .5movv \text{ for } v \ll c \quad ((8))$$

$.5movv$ is the Newtonian kinetic energy obtained by accelerating a center-of-mass and seems to have nothing to do with a complex wavelike interaction linked with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. It is nevertheless the Newtonian $.5mvv$ which appears in E which, in turn, appears in this wavelike object. This suggests that even though the c-signal is associated with a kind of mathematical probability structure $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, this structure is, in turn, linked to center-of-mass dynamics. Thus, one does not separate the so-called wave structure from the particle.

We further note that one does not have a physical wave situation for $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, even in a 2-slit experiment. A particle with p and $KE = .5movv$ approaches a 2-slit apparatus. If the interaction were based on the center-of-mass (or a tiny radius about it), the particle would pass through one of the slits without interacting at all. The c-signal, linked to conservation of momentum, however, indicates that one has interaction in space in range $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and so if the slits are separated by this distance, the particle may actually interact with one or the other. The problem now becomes probabilistic, but one still retains the particle view, because one assumes that one has a ray $\exp(i p \cdot r_1)$ from the center of one slit and $\exp(ip \cdot r_2)$

from the center of the other. This means that one has a particle in mind and that it will either go through one slit or the other. The math is an interference of the two views given by:

$$|\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1) + \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)|^2 \quad ((9))$$

Assuming r_1 and r_2 are almost parallel if a screen is very far away, one has $r_1 = r_2 + d \sin(\theta)$ where θ is made with the y-axis and the slits are along the x. One obtains an interference pattern, but this is a probabilistic approach (not a physical wave which passes through both slits). Ultimately, a single particle passes through one slit and has its trajectory bent, but moves with the same magnitude of p . One really has a kinetic energy wave as $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ is moving through space, but one does not know at what angle it will move. The mathematical $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ together with a particle viewpoint allows one to compute this interaction which is due to the large range $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ due to the c signals.

Bound State Example

Given that one does not have a physical wave, one does not have intensity spread out in a medium. Rather, we argue, one has energy (kinetic energy in the nonrelativistic case) which moves according to a pattern created by an interference scheme based on $\exp(ipx)$ due to signals linked to an interaction. In a bound state problem, one has interaction with a potential and so for a single particle, there are probabilities $\exp(ip_1x)$, $\exp(ip_2x)$ etc (1-D). One would then propose:

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad \text{where } a(p) \text{ is a weight} \quad ((10))$$

There is interference in ((10)) like in the 2-slit case, but here one really should have a energy like wave wave, i.e. $pp/2m$ for each $\exp(ipx)$ which the $\exp(ipx)$'s still interfering. Thus, we suggest that that appropriate energy entity is:

$$\sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \quad ((11))$$

((11)) seems to be a clear example of a particle and wave together, not separate.

The question then is what does one do with ((11)) which represents a kind of average kinetic energy wave? We suggest that ((10)) which represents interaction should be combined with $V(x)$ because it is the overall interaction which is relevant. ((11)) is a free particle energy wave which must exist because $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with free kinetic energy of $pp/2m$ while still interacting with $V(x)$. Thus, one has:

$$((11)) + V(x) ((10)) = E ((10)) \quad \text{we suggest} \quad ((12))$$

E multiplied by ((10)) means that the overall energy is the same at each x point, i.e. the overall system may be represented by $\exp(-iEt)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued it is not an accident that special relativity for a particle with rest mass contains the frame-invariant speed c in equations for E and p . E and p are properties of the particle, but a moving particle has been accelerated in the Newtonian scheme and is linked with Newton's equations and conservation of momentum and energy. These physical notions cannot disappear simply because one applies special relativistic complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ relative to each other. We suggest that $-Et+px \neq 0$ applies to center-of-mass motion of a particle with rest mass, but because of the c signals present (linked with interaction), there should be a second solution $-Et+px = 0$ (like that for a free photon). This leads to the notion of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, a kind of math-complex rotation-wavelike probability linked both to interaction and center-of-mass E, p properties. One uses $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is not a fixed property of a particle, but rather linked to interaction and we argue that it is essential in physically ensuring conservation of momentum and energy. Thus, these conservation laws do not disappear from special relativity.

This, however, leads to a quantum mechanical viewpoint, but one which intertwines a particle viewpoint with an $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ one. In the 2-slit experiment, one writes $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1)$ and $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)$ as if one has a particle at each slit. The interference of the two $\exp()$ s leads to a probability pattern, but ultimately a single particle moves along one of these straight line trajectories to the wall. In the bound state case, one has various $\exp(ipx)$ s, but these are related to center-of-mass $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ energies (nonrelativistic) and so it is a kind of kinetic energy probability scenario which is present. At the same \sum over $a(p) \exp(ipx)$ interacts with $V(x)$ and the overall result must be $E \sum$ over $p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ because one has $\exp(-Et)$ which does not distinguish points in space.